

Utilising side streams from a reverse osmosis water treatment plant for production of brine for fish salting

Nýting hliðarstrauma frá vatnshreinsistöð sem byggir á sameindasíun á sjó til framleiðslu á pækli fyrir fisksöltun

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Ágríp á íslensku:	<p>Frá 1968 þegar vatnsleiðsla var fyrst tengd á milli Vestmannaeyja og fastalandsins hafa Eyjabúar reitt sig á aðgengi að ferskvatni í gegnum plastleiðslur sem liggja á hafsbötni. Vestmannaeyingar og atvinnulífið á Eyjunni voru þó óþyrmilega minntir á það óryggi sem felst af því að vera háðir slíkri tengingu varðandi lífsnauðsynjar 2023 þegar skemmdir urðu á leiðslunni. Í framhaldi fjárfestu fyrirtæki á svæðinu í vatnshreinsibúnaði sem framleitt getur ferskvatn úr sjó. Vinnslustöðin í Vestmannaeyjum fjárfesti meðal annast í slíkum búnaði, og í framhaldi kom upp sú hugmynd hvort ekki væri hægt að nýta þá hliðarstrauma sem til verða við ferskvatnsframleiðsluna. En vatnshreinsistöðin síar steinefni og óhreinindi úr sjónum, þannig að eftir verður hreint vatn. Meðal þeirra steinefna sem síast frá er salt, en Vinnslustöðin er á sama tíma að flytja inn töluvert magn af salti til saltfiskframleiðslu. Það lá því beinast við að kanna möguleikann á að nýta saltpækil sem fellur til við ferskvatnsframleiðsluna fyrir saltfiskvinnslu. Vinnslustöðin fékk því Matís með sér í lið til að kanna fýsileika þess, og fengu auk þess stuðning frá LÓU sjóðnum til að fjármagna hluta af verkefninu. Markmið verkefnisins var að kanna fýsileika þess að nýta salt frá ferskvatnsframleiðslunni til saltfiskframleiðslu m.t.t. matvælaöryggis, afkasta, kostnaðar og sjálfbærni.</p> <p>Helstu niðurstöður sýndu að hægt er að nota pækilinn (RO-brine) í forsöltun án þess að skerða gæði vörunnar, lit eða sýrustig (pH). Vinnslutilraunirnar sýndu sambærilegar niðurstöður hvað varðar saltmagn í lokaafurðinni og engin neikvæð áhrif á afköstin. Í heildina gæti notkun þessa pækils dregið verulega úr saltinnflutningi til saltfiskframleiðslu, sem gæti leitt til umtalsverðrar lækkunar á kostnaði við framleiðslu saltfisks. Enn fremur sýndi vistferilsmat (LCA) fram á að með því að nýta pækilinn má draga verulega úr umhverfisáhrifum framleiðslunnar, samanborið við hefðbundinn pækil sem framleiddur er úr innfluttu salti.</p> <p>Sýnt hefur því verið fram á í verkefninu að notkun saltpækils sem fellur til við vatnshreinsun sé tæknilega raunhæfur, hagkvæmur og sjálfbærari valkostur við saltfiskframleiðslu.</p>		
Lykilorð á íslensku:	Vatnshreinsistöð, saltfiskframleiðsla, saltpækill, vistferilsgreining, LCA		

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<p><i>Summary in English:</i></p>	<p>Since 1968, when a freshwater pipeline was first connected between the Westman Islands and the mainland, the islanders have relied on access to freshwater through plastic pipelines that lie on the seabed. The inhabitants of the Islands and its industries were harshly reminded of the insecurity of being dependent on such a connection for their essential needs in 2023 when the pipeline was damaged. Subsequently, companies in the area invested in water treatment plants that can produce freshwater from seawater. Westmann islands largest seafood company and the largest workplace, Vinnslustöðin (VSV) invested in such equipment, and subsequently the idea arose of whether it would be possible to utilize the side streams that are created during the production of freshwater. But the water treatment plant filters minerals and impurities from the sea, so that only clean water remains. Among the minerals that are filtered out is salt, but VSV is at the same time importing considerable amounts of salt for its saltfish production. The focus was therefore on investigating the possibility of using the salt brine that is generated from the freshwater production for saltfish processing. VSV therefore brought Mátis on board to investigate its feasibility and also received support from the LÓU Fund to finance part of the project. The aim of the project was to investigate the feasibility of using salt from freshwater production for saltfish production in terms of food safety, yield, cost and sustainability.</p> <p>The main results showed that the brine can be used in pre-salting without compromising the quality of the product, colour or pH. The processing experiments showed comparable results in terms of salt content in the final product and no negative impact on performance or yield. Overall, the use of the brine could substantially reduce salt imports for saltfish production, which could lead to a significant reduction in the cost of producing salted fish. Furthermore, a life cycle assessment (LCA) showed that by utilizing the brine, the environmental impact of production can be substantially reduced, compared to traditional brine produced from imported salt.</p> <p>The project has therefore demonstrated that the use of salt brine generated during water purification process using reverse osmosis is a technically feasible, economical and more sustainable alternative to current practises for saltfish production.</p>
<p><i>English keywords:</i></p>	<p><i>Saltfish production, Water treatment plant, Brine, LCA, Water re-use</i></p>

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1 Introduction

Westman Islands (Vestmannaeyjar) is an archipelago located about 10 km off the south coast of Iceland. The largest island is Heimaey, which is the home of almost 5,000 people and thriving industries that revolve mostly on fisheries and seafood production. Since 1968, when a water pipeline was first connected between the Westman Islands and the mainland, the islanders have relied on access to freshwater through plastic pipes that lie on the seabed. The inhabitants of the Westman Islands and the island's business community were however reminded of the insecurity of being dependent on such a fragile infrastructure for their essential needs in 2023, when the pipeline was damaged. Subsequently, companies in the area invested in water purification systems that can produce freshwater from seawater. The Island's largest employer, Vinnslustöðin hf (VSV), invested in such a system, and subsequently the idea arose whether it would be possible to utilise the side streams that are created during the freshwater production. But the water purification plant filters minerals and impurities from the seawater, so that only clean drinking water remains. Among the minerals that are filtered out is salt, but VSV is at the same time importing a considerable amount of salt for its saltfish production. The focus was therefore on investigating the possibility of using the salt from freshwater production for salted fish production. The processing plant therefore brought Matís on board to investigate the applicability and feasibility of using the filtered salt for saltfish processing. VSV also contracted the supplier of the water purification system Hatlenboer-Water BV to assist with the analysis, and in addition received support from the LÓU fund to take part in funding the project.

The aim of the project was to investigate the feasibility of using salt from freshwater production for salted fish production in terms of food safety, quality, yield, cost and sustainability. The project was broken into the following work packages:

1. Applicability and cost-benefit assessment
2. Quality, yield and food safety
3. Environmental impacts & Life Cycle Assessment
4. Communication and dissemination
5. Project management

2 Applicability and cost-benefit assessment

The aim of work package 3 was to assess the economic feasibility of utilising the salt coming as a byproduct in VSV's water treatment plant for saltfish processing. The assessment was divided into two phases, as the first phase focused on examining the equipment that was already installed at VSV for processes freshwater from seawater. The equipment comes from the Dutch company Hatlenboer-water, and a description of the processing process is shown in Figure 1 (I. Zeiner, J. A. Suul, A. Marcos and M. Molinas, 2014).

Figure 1: The set-up of the water purification process

The process is a membrane filtration based on reverse osmosis (RO), as shown in Figure 2. In this phase, the salt concentration in the brine that is generated during freshwater production is increased from 3.3-3.7% to 5.5-6.0%. Membrane filtration is used to remove smaller particles from liquids that are not visible, and this technology can be classified into several subcategories: microfiltration (MF), ultrafiltration (UF), nanofiltration (NF) and reverse osmosis (RO). The pore size in filtration affects their effectiveness, and also the pressure and flow rate during filtration through the membranes (See Appendixes). Membrane filtration provides the possibility of isolating different particles by size and thereby achieving classification of different substances. The VSV equipment is built with spiral membranes (spiral UF). The equipment is economical in operation due to, among other things, low energy consumption, good durability of the spiral membranes, good chemical and thermal stability, a service life of up to several years, etc.

Figure 2: The membrane filtration (reverse osmosis module)

In the second phase, experts at Hatenboer-water were contacted to see if they could come up with a solution that would significantly increase the salt concentration of the brine from the RO equipment. They conducted experiments at their facility in the Netherlands and then came up with a proposal that could increase the salt concentration to 8.7% and the UHP-RO brine solution became much cleaner. The proposal was based on a two-stage system where the first stage was nanofiltration (NF) that was intended to reduce the concentration of copper (Cu), calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) in the brine, and the second stage was a membrane filtration with ultra-high pressure (Ultra High-Pressure Reverse osmosis, UHP-RO). Figure 3 shows the setup of the proposed system.

Figure 3: Setup of the proposed system to increase the salt concentration

2.1 Applicability of the current system

By setting up a chemical balance for the VSV RO-unit and using assumptions from the manufacturer that the equipment's capacity is 54 m³/h of seawater, and then using dry matter (DM) measurements in the chemical measurements, it can be estimated that the equipment can produce about 20 tons of freshwater per hour and at the same time about 34 tons of RO-brine are produced as a side stream during water purification, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Chemical balance across the RO equipment

It is important to pause here to examine how much the dry matter content of the sea has a significant effect, for example, if the dry matter is 3.3% instead of 3.7%, the capacity would be about 24 tons of freshwater per hour and about 575 tons per day. The chemical contents of the seawater, freshwater and the salt brine is also extremely important, but the results of the chemical measurements are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Results of chemical analysis from the RO-membrane filtration

	Units	sea water	RO-water	RO-Brine
Dry matter	%	3,70	<0,01	5,90
Na	g/l	10,90	0,02	18,20
K	mg/l	363,60	0,70	600,00
Ca	mg/l	458,40	6,20	759,90
Mg	mg/l	1.290,00	0,30	2.161,40
Fe	µg/l	6,94	2,97	5,54
Ni	µg/l	0,40	0,10	0,10
Cu	µg/l	1,59	0,17	1,45
Mn	µg/l	0,22	1,37	1,82

A prerequisite for the project as a whole is the assumption that the chemical composition of the RO-brine is favourable for salt fish processing. If the chemical contents are slightly off, the quality of the final product will be affected. To better understand the results of the chemical analysis, the concentration of the minerals and other chemicals must be monitored and calculated. Table 2 shows the standard of Icelandic saltfish producers, which was created to ensure that Icelandic salted fish is of the correct quality.

Table 2: The salt standard for Icelandic saltfish producer.

			Faulted	Good	Faulted	Unusable
Main ingredients	NaCl	% On dry basis		> 98%	<96%	<95%
	Water	%		< 3,5%	>3.5%	>5%
Additional ingredients	Calcium	%Ca	< 0,05%	0,05-0,20%	0,20-0,35%	> 0,35%
		CaSO ₄	< 0,17%	0,17-0,70%	0,70-1,19%	> 1,19%
	Magnesium	%Mg		< 0,1%		> 0,1%
		%MgSO ₄		< 0,5%		> 0,5%
Contaminants	Copper	mg Cu/kg		< 0,03mg	0,03-0,05mg	> 0,05mg
	Iron	mg Fe/kg		< 10mg		> 10mg
	Manganese	mg Mn/kg		< 2mg		> 2mg
	Zink	mg Zn/kg				
Microorganisms	Red-halophilic bacteria	pr. g		< 100.000	100.000-1.000.000	>1.000.000
Dirt	Sand, soil, organic matter	g		< 0,03g	0,03-0,045g	> 0,45g
Lykt	Olie	%		< 0,01%	0,01-0,03%	> 0,03%
Grain size	< 1mm	%		4-12%	>12%	
	> 4mm	%		8-24%	>24%	

To compare the chemical analysis of the RO-brine with the Icelandic standard, it is necessary to calculate the substances on a dry basis and have them with the same units as used in the salt standard, which is done in Table 3.

Table 3: Chemical composition of the RO-brine on dry matter basis.

		On dry basis	Measured
Main ingredients	NaCl	%	78,4%
	Water	%	0
Additional ingredients	Calcium	%Ca	1,3%
	Magnesium	%Mg	3,7%
Contaminants	Copper	mg Cu/kg	0,025
	Iron	mg Fe/kg	0,094
	Manganese	mg Mn/kg	0,031
	Nikkel	mg Zn/kg	0,002

When the tables are compared, it is apparent that the chemical composition of the RO-brine does not meet the requirements for several substances, including NaCl, which is measured at 78.4% on a dry basis, which is much lower than the standard states. This is due to the fact that the contents of other substances are at higher values. The metals iron, copper, manganese and nickel are far below the limits set out in the salt standard and should therefore not affect the oxidation of fat (runoff) in salted fish and therefore there should be less risk of product discoloration due to oxidation of fat in fish muscle, i.e. yellowing, thus preventing products from meeting the correct market quality. The calcium (Ca) content is measured at 1.3% in the RO brine, which is about 4 times too high, while the standard reference value is 0.2-0.35%, and the magnesium (Mg) content is measured at 3.7%, which should ideally be below 0.1%. Calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) affect the colour, taste, texture and how dense the surface of the fish is. Calcium improves the quality of fish by preserving the light appearance. If the concentration of these substances is too high, they can have a negative effect, the surface of the fish can harden too much, and this can even cause under-salting. Other substances meet the standard's

limit values. The RO-brine can be used in the brining of salted fish, which is the first step in the salted fish processing cycle and is called pre-salting before dry salting, which is the main processing step in the processing of fully processed salted fish. In order to investigate whether these deviations in the chemical content of the RO-brine will have an effect on the quality of the product, a thorough study of the reaction process was set up and two groups were studied, namely a traditional process and a process with the RO-brine (see chapter 3).

2.2 Cost-benefit assessment of the current system for freshwater production

As soon as the freshwater pipeline between Westmann islands and the mainland damaged, the security of the municipality and the industries on the island was threatened. VSV reacted by investing in the water treatment unit from Hatnboer. The primary purpose of the unit is to secure VSV with freshwater, but it has an overcapacity so that it could also supply the municipality with freshwater if needed. In fact, the price of freshwater is significantly higher in Westmann islands than on the mainland of Iceland, meaning that having an alternative supplier of freshwater could be of strategic importance for the municipality.

The water treatment unit is compact and can be fitted in containers if needed. Figure 5 shows the system as it is set up at VSV.

Figure 5: The water treatment plant at VSV

The initial cost of the water treatment unit was around 100 million ISK (650,000 EUR). Key figures regarding the unit's capacity and energy needs are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Key figures for one container-unit freshwater production plant

Feed flow during service (m ³ /h)	54,3
Capacity fresh water (output) (m ³ /day):	600
Recovery:	46%
Power installed per RO system (kW):	~ 80
Power consumption per RO system (kW):	~66
Energy demand produced water(kWh/m ³)	3,6

Based on the chemical measurements of material streams and by applying mass accounting calculations to the results, it can be seen that the recovery of freshwater is 37.3%, as already shown in Figure 4.

It is estimated that the RO unit will be able to deliver about 480 tons of freshwater per 24 hours, at full capacity. The energy consumption was recalculated and is now estimated to be slightly higher (5%) than indicated by the manufacturer, and as a result the energy cost is expected to be 82.5 ISK/ton of freshwater, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Estimated electricity costs for producing one ton of RO water and comparison of figures from the equipment supplier and from the VSV team

	Power	Electr. Consum	Energy Requirements for RO-water	Energy Cost of RO Water
	kW	kWh/day	kWh/ton RO-water	kr/ton RO-water
Consumed energy for RO-unit	66	1584	3,26	71,7
Add. energy for the unit - estim. 15% of cons. power	9,9	237,6	0,49	10,8
Re-estimated consumed energy	75,9	1821,6	3,75	82,5
Energy demand from Tech. quot. for RO-units from H.Water			3,6	79,2

A rough estimate of the operating costs, including the capital costs, of producing freshwater with the RO unit is presented in Table 6. The estimated cost per ton is around 205 ISK/m³, but this cost could be lower if the side streams would be utilised to create value (thereby sharing the cost of the operating costs). To put this in perspective, the current cost of VSV when purchasing each m³ of freshwater from the mainland is 245 ISK (consisting of a fixed fee of 84 ISK, meter rental 7 ISK and usage 154 ISK). There could therefore be a considerable benefit from using the RO equipment from Hatenboer-Water to produce freshwater, in addition to the possible utilisation of side streams and the security of not being dependant on freshwater from the mainland.

Table 6: Estimated operating costs for the VSV RO unit for the production of freshwater

Cost item	ISK/m ³	%
Energy cost ²	82,5	40%
Spear parts	8,0	4%
Membranes	10,0	5%
Chemicals	5,0	2%
Labour	8,0	4%
Maintenance	7,0	3%
Other costs	5,0	2%
Capital cost ³	79,1	39%
Cost per m³ of freshwater	204,6	100%

2.3 Cost-benefit assessment of the current system for salt brine production

During the freshwater production in the RO system a side-stream of salt brine is generated. This brine is potentially ideal to be utilised for pre-salting at VSV, but the pre-salting is the first step in the salting process for the production of fully processed salted fish. When production of saltfish, the first step is brining which uses brine with a salt concentration of 15-20%, and for the purpose of this project the concentration is set at 16% and the ratio between split fish and brine is 1:1,8.

Table 7 shows that 1,250 tons of split fish and 2,250 tons of salt brine are needed to produce 1,000 tons of fully processed salted fish. To produce the brine in the conventional way a total of 360 tons of salt are needed, but by using RO-brine instead of water it is possible to save 119 tons of salt and 1,890 tons of freshwater. The price of the salt that VSV is using is about 23 thousand ISK/ton (150 EUR/ton) and the price of freshwater is 245 ISK/m³, meaning that the savings of using RO brine instead of the conventional method would be about 2.7 million ISK in salt purchases and 0.5 million ISK in freshwater costs.

Table 7: the benefits of using the RO brine in the pre-salting of fully processed salted fish. a) comparison of salt usage in the production of 16% brine from salt and salt + RO-brine, b) calculated amount of flatfish to produce 1,000 tons of fully processed salted fish based on 80% efficiency

a)

Salt use in pre-salting	Salt	Water	RO-brine	Brine needed for producing 1,000 t. of fully cured saltfish	Salt	Δm _s
Brine (16%) - conventional	16,0	84,0		2.250	360	
Brine (16%) - RO brine	10,7			2.250	241	119

b)

Curing yield	80%
Split fish (t.)	1.250
Fully cured saltfish (t.)	1.000

² Energy cost 22 ISK/kWh

³ Initial investment & instillation cost of 125 million ISK, 7% interest rates and 15-year depreciation time

This would to about 3.2 million ISK in cost reduction when producing 1,000 tons of fully processed salted fish, and if VSV produces around 4,500 tons of salted fish a year, the savings would amount to about 14.5 million ISK annually.

2.4 Cost-benefit assessment of an additional filtration system

It soon became apparent that it was desirable to reduce the concentration of Mg, Ca and Cu in the RO-brine and Hatenboer-Water was therefore contacted to propose an additional filtration system that could reduce the concentration of these undesirable minerals. After considering the equipment that the company produces, a proposal was made to install an additional processing process. Hatenboer set up a pilot production line at their facility and conducted experiments with this production line and then proposed a solution that could increase the salt concentration of the UHPRO-brine to 8.7% (dry solids content). The solution involved using a two-stage system where the first stage was nanofiltration (NF) and it was intended to reduce the concentration of copper (Cu), calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) in the brine, and the second stage was an ultra-high pressure membrane filter (Ultra High-Pressure Reverse osmosis, UHP-RO) aimed at increasing the sodiumsalt (NaCl) concentration considerably. Figure 6 shows the basic setup of the system.

Figure 6: An overview of a process design to further concentrate the RO-brine and remove unwanted substances while simultaneously reducing the Mg, Ca and Cu content in the brine. Pilot equipment from Hatenboer-Water.

The measurement done by Hatenboer showed that favourable results could be achieved with the implementation of this additional processing process and equipment, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Results from the measurements of RO-brine and UHPRO-brine from different processing processes at Hatenboer-Water.

	Wet basis		Dry basis	
	Container RO-brine	UHP RO concentrated brine	Container RO-brine	UHP RO concentrated brine
TDS (%)	5,38	8,70	100	100
SodiumChloride (NaCl) (%)	4,0	8,2	74,7	93,7
PotassiumChloride (KCl) (%)	0,11	0,23	2,10	2,61
Calcium (Ca) (%)	0,08	0,06	1,47	0,66
Magnesium (Mg) (%)	0,20	0,03	3,80	0,37
Copper (Cu) (mg/kg)	1,45	1,18	0,27	0,025

To gain full understanding of these results, it is best to assess them on dry matter basis. The salt concentration of NaCl increases significantly with this additional step, or from 74.7% to 93.7% and interestingly, KCl also increases to 2.61% (a relative increase of about 25%). The results are very interesting for Ca, where the content is measured at about 45% of what it is in the RO-brine, for Mg it is only about 10% and Cu is about 9% of the content measured in the RO-brine. It is worth examining the dry matter in these brines, but the total salt content is 82.0% in RO-brine and 97.1% in UHPRO-brine, so it can be seen that some impurities (including organic matter) are cleaned out with this additional step. These results show that the additional unit proposed by Hatenboer would meet the requirements set by VSV to increase the salt concentration and filter out undesirable minerals and impurities.

The investment- and running cost of the additional unit is considerable, with initial cost of about 23 million ISK (162,000 EUR) and additional 7-10 million ISK for shipping and installation. The energy needed for running the unit is also significant, amounting to about 20 kWh/m³, as shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Key figures for the NF-UHPRO pilot unit

Nanofiltration	
Feed flow during service (m ³ /h)	2,32
FF wastewater (output) (m ³ /h)	0,93
NF product (m ³ /h)	1,39
Ultra High Pressure RO	
Capacity fresh water (output) (m ³ /h)	0,78
UHPRO-brine (output) (m ³ /h)	0,61
NF-UHPRO system	
Power installed per NF-UHPRO system (kW)	~ 18
Power consumption per NF-UHPRO system (kW)	~ 15
Energy demand produced UHPRO-brine (kWh/m ³)	~ 20

The energy consumption alone would therefore add 440 ISK/m³ in addition to the investment-, maintenance- and other costs. For the time being VSV has therefore decided not to invest in the NF-

UHPRO system, as the applicability of using the brine for saltfish production has still only been tested on pilot scale. When long-term proof of concept, with large volumes of saltfish having been produced, sold and consumed; a decision can be made if the additional unit should be purchased or not.

3 Quality, yield and food safety when using RO brine

Traditional brining methods rely on fresh water mixed with salt to prepare the brine-solution but following the investment of VSV in a water treatment plant, the company decided to explore the option of using the brine (RO-brine) that comes as side stream from the filtration process as ingredient in the brine-solution. The challenges that must be addressed to assess the applicability of such an approach include ensuring that quality, yield and food safety is not negatively affected. To assess that, two trials were done testing both the impact of the brine concentration and the type of brine used.

3.1 Material and methods

First trial

A total of 100 Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*) were used in this study. The fish were caught near Westmann islands by Drangavik VE 80, a bottom trawler, between the 10th and 11th April 2025. The fish was landed on the 12th of April and subsequently processed on the 15th of April 2025. During onboard handling, the fish were gutted, chilled in seawater and stored in ice slurry. Upon landing they were kept refrigerated at 2 C until transfer to the processing facility.

For the salting experiment, food-grade sea salt from Saltkaup, (origin: Tunisia) was used. The salt and RO-brine (side-stream from the desalting container) had the composition detailed in Table 10.

Table 10: composition of the brine and the salt

	Side-stream from the RO-unite (RO-brine)	Salt – Saltkaup; Origin: Tunisia
Dry matter (%)	5.90	97.5
NaCl (%)	4.42	95.7
KCl (%)	0.11	0.2
CaCl ₂ (in %)	0.21	0.5
MgCl ₂ (in %)	0.71	0.5
Iron (Fe) (in mg/kg)	1.11	1.8
Copper (Cu) (in mg/kg)	0,25	003
Manganese (Mn) (in mg/kg)	0,04	1,2

During the project two different brining methods were tested, traditional brine made from fresh water and salt and container brine (RO-brine) made from side stream from the Reverse Osmosis freshwater generator (RO-water). Figure 7 summarises how the two processes were done.

Figure 7: Salting process of the cod with traditional brine and RO-brine.

Cod salting process

The process of producing fully cured heavy salted cod products is divided into two stages, the first stage is brining (1-4 days), and the second stage is dry salting (18-22 days). After the second stage of process, the liquid in the fish muscle is saturated brine (water activity as $a_w = 0,76-0,78$) and the product is stable in storage under the right conditions, that is, a relative humidity of 78% and a temperature of $0^\circ - +4^\circ\text{C}$.

Brining

Cod are immersed in approximately 15% salt brine for 24 hours. In VSV, the brine concentration is checked with a density measurement method. The fish and brine are set in tubs and stored in the cold storage. In the experiment, two types of brines are prepared, first a brine mixture was prepared using RO-brine which was made stronger by adding salt to achieve the right strength and secondly a traditional brine of the same strength is made by mixing fresh water with dry salt.

RO-brine: As the salt content of RO-brine was about 6% and to increase the strength, dry salt was added. The final salt content was measured with the density meter and showed a salt content of 14%. 50 split cod of an average weight $2754.2 \pm 692.4\text{g}$ were brined for 24h.

Traditional brine: A brine with an estimated 16% (measured with the density meter) salt content was made by mixing dry salt into fresh water. 50 split cod of an average weight of $2714.7 \pm 530.5\text{g}$ were brined for 24h.

Dry Salting

After brining, all the fish were subjected to dry salting for 21 days under controlled conditions. Dry salting took place in a 660L tub which was filled with salt and fish, with an alternance of layers of fish and salt to ensure a full coverage of the fish.

Storage

After the dry salting, the fully cured salted fish is placed in storage under controlled conditions. VSV is closed for around two months in the summer, therefore the cod that is initially salted before the closure, will stay in storage for approximately 3 months (counting the transport and storage time) before being delivered to the sellers or retailers. The fully salted fish are set in cardboard boxes in salt

during 3 months in a fridge at around 4°C and relative humidity about 78%. The temperature and relative humidity in the storage have been recorded with a logger (i-button, Embedded data System) and the conditions shown that the average temperature was around 5°C and the average relative humidity around 78% as shown on Figure 8.

Figure 8: a) Temperature and humidity (top) in the cold- store; b)Core temperature of the fish (bottom) stored in tubs for drysalting.

Second trial

The aim of the second trial was to study the effects further of using RO-brine compared to traditional brine. The RO-brine used in the first trial had lower salt content than what the density meter showed, most likely because of other types of salt, therefore the brine concentration was measured using a refractometer. The first trial showed that the RO-brine at lower brine concentration gave better curing yield (or total yield) than the traditional brine. Therefore, in the second trial both brining methods were studied at 7% and 15% brine concentration to confirm, resulting in four groups studied in the second trial.

A total of 40 cod were used in this trial. The fish was caught again by Drangavík VE80, near Westmann islands, on September 18th and splitted five days later the September 23rd. The split fish were divided into the four groups, 10 in each group. The fish were processed the same way as in the first trial but without 3 months of storage.

Measurements:

In both trials the weight of the individual split fish was recorded, at each processing step (initial, post brining, post dry salting). In the 1st trial, 10 fish per group went through 3 months of storage and were weighed after. For the 1st trial, 10 fishes from each group were also analysed for colour and pH initially, post brining, post salting and after storage. At each step, the chemical composition of the fish was analysed in triplicates, and the brines were also chemically analysed before and after brining.

Weight, dry yield and mass balance

Individual fish were weighed at each step to get an average value per group. Total yield, curing yield and weight loss during storage (in %) were calculated as the ratio of the final weight to the initial raw fish weight, expressed as percentage.

The mass balance based on the salt free dry matter of the salting process was calculated on a reference of 100kg. The Z^{NaCl} value was also calculated as follow: $Z^{NaCl} = \text{concentration of salt} / (\text{concentration of salt} + \text{concentration of water})$.

Colour measurements

The colour of the fish was measured in the 1st trial. The colour measurements were done with a Minolta Chroma Meter CR-400 (Minolta, Osaka, Japan) using the CIE Lab system. L-value indicates the lightness ranking from 0 (dark) to 100 (light). The a-value indicates the change from green (negative values) to red (positive values) and the b-value indicates the blue (negative values) to yellow (positive values). The colour was measured on three point on the cut of the split cod (as shown on Figure 9).

The whiteness and yellowness of the samples were also evaluated. Whiteness was calculated according to the equation developed by Judd and Wyszecki in 1963.

$$Whiteness_{Judd} = 100 - \sqrt{(100 - abs(L))^2 + abs(a)^2 + abs(b)^2}$$

Figure 9: Colour measurements on split cod

The yellowness was calculated according to the formula developed by Francis and Clydesdale in 1975.

$$Yellowness_{FC} = 142.86 * \frac{abs(b)}{abs(L)}$$

pH measurements

The pH of the split fish was also only done in the 1st trial and was taken as an average value of the 3 samples, measured each as triplicate (one close to the top, one in the middle back piece and one in the back close to the tail, close to where the colour was measured as shown in Figure 9). The pH meter was a Portavo 902 (Knick international, Germany) with the pH sensor SE 104 N (Knick international, Germany) and ranged from pH 2 to pH 13. It was calibrated before each use.

Chemical composition and mineral analysis

Proximate composition (water, protein, salt) and mineral concentrations (iron, copper, manganese) were determined for three cod at each step in the 1st trial. In the first trial, the initial fish were also measured for potassium, calcium and magnesium and the two brines were measured both before the fish were set in and after they were removed. In the second trial, proximate composition (protein, water and salt) was measured after the brining and dry salting steps on three fish as well. The brines

were as well measured for mineral concentrations before the brining process but not after because minimal effects were seen in the 1st trial.

The water content was measured according to the ISO 6496-1999 method. The fat content was measured according to the Soxhlet method, with the method AOCS Ba 3-38 (2017). The protein content was measured according to the Kjeldahl method with the method ISO 16634-1:2008(E). The salt content was measured according to the method AOAC (2000). 17th ed no.976.18. The iron, copper, magnesium, calcium and Manganese content were measured according to the method NMKL 186 (2007), modified.

Statistical analysis

For the statistical analysis of the weight in the first trial, the Welch Two Sample t-test was conducted as the groups were independent but with unequal variances. For the second test as the data was nonparametric and the number of replicates was lower, a Kruskal Wallis test was done followed by a Dunn pairwise comparison test, when the Kruskal Wallis showed a significant difference. The statistical analysis was run on R version 4.3.1 (2023). As only triplicates were run for the other measurements, an average and standard deviation error were calculated.

3.2 Results and discussion

First trial

Brines

The brine compositions were analysed before and after having the fish in them for 24h. Brines were made using a density meter for measuring salt concentration since analysing the chemical composition takes time. The composition of the brines before and after the brining are shown in Table 11.

The salt (NaCl) content in the RO-brine was only 7.7%, while for the traditional brine it was 15.8%. This difference could be explained by the method used to measure the salt content in the beginning. The density meter could be impacted by the presence of other salt forms, such as magnesium chloride, potassium chloride and calcium chloride, as they were all higher in the RO-brine than the traditional one. This shows the need for another method to measure salt content than density meter since the density measurements are biased by other salt forms present in it.

Table 11: Composition of the brines used before and after brining.

	Brine before		Brine after	
	Traditional	RO-brine	Traditional	RO-brine
NaCl in %	15,86	7,72	15,61	7,59
Calcium (g/kg)	0,08	0,38	0,13	0,36
Magnesium (g/kg)	0,08	0,92	0,11	0,92
Potassium (g/kg)	0,03	0,32	0,67	0,68
Iron (mg/kg)	0,43	0,17	0,37	0,3
Copper (mg/kg)	<0.01	<0.01	0,008	0,008
Manganese (mg/kg)	0,04	0,01	0,02	0,01

After brining the fish for 24h, the composition of the brines changed slightly. The salt content was reduced, by approximately 0.2% and the amount of potassium, calcium and magnesium increased in the traditional brine. This increase can be explained by the exchanges that happen with the fish, as their levels of these minerals were higher than their presence in the brine.

Weight changes

The weight of the individual split fish of the two groups was followed through each production step. Each group had 50 individual split fish. The average weight after each step of the process can be found below in **Error! Reference source not found.** Overall, the initial weight of the fish in the 2 groups was similar (no significant difference found, p-value: 0,33) and as expected, after brining, the weight increased in both groups. However, the weight after brining was significantly higher in the RO-brine group compared to the traditional group (p-value < 0,05). The difference of weight in the final salted groups was not significant. However, when the weight was considered as weight loss between the initial and salting steps, the traditional group had lost significantly more weight than the container group (p-value < 0,05).

Table 12: Weight change in the 1st trial after each processing step and final curing yield.

<u>Processing step</u>	<u>Traditional</u>	<u>RO-brine</u>
Initial (g)	2715 ± 530	2754 ± 692
Brining (g)	2731 ± 514	2914 ± 714
Brining (%)	0,8 ± 3,4	6,1 ± 2,4
Salting (g)	1791 ± 378	1940 ± 483
Salting (%)	-33,9 ± 6,5	-29,3 ± 4,2
Storage (g)	1866 ± 360	2012 ± 368
Storage (%)	7,8 ± 7,4	-1,2 ± 6,1

Chemical analysis of fish

Chemical measurements of the fish were analysed at each processing step and are shown in Table 13. After the first step, brining, the fish brined with traditional brine took in more salt and had lower protein content than fish brined using the RO-brine. The difference however evened out over the dry salting step where no significant difference was seen between groups.

Table 13: Chemical composition of the fish at each processing step.

	<u>Initial</u>	<u>After brining</u>		<u>After dry salting</u>		<u>After storage</u>	
	<u>Fish</u>	<u>Traditional</u>	<u>RO-brine</u>	<u>Traditional</u>	<u>RO-brine</u>	<u>Traditional</u>	<u>RO-brine</u>
Water (%)	82,1 ± 0,9	78,5 ± 0,5	80,7 ± 0,4	57,5 ± 0,8	57,4 ± 0,7	56,2 ± 0,2	56,1 ± 0,3
Protein (%)	16,6 ± 0,8	14,9 ± 1,3	16,1 ± 0,8	20,5 ± 0,5	20,0 ± 1,4	21,3 ± 0,7	21,6 ± 0,5
Salt (%)	0,5 ± 0,3	5,7 ± 1,3	2,7 ± 0,6	21,5 ± 1,1	21,9 ± 2,1	21,4 ± 0,8	20,7 ± 0,7

Mass balance and Yields

The mass balance evaluation of the process was done through the evaluation of three parameters: First the weight change/curing yield on weight basis, then the weight change or curing yield on a salt free dry-matter basis and then through the calculation of the Z_{NaCl} value, representing the salt concentration of the water within the fish (Table 14).

Table 14: Curing yields first trial

Group	Traditional brine	RO-brine
Yield (by weight)	66.9%	71.3%
Yield (by salt free d.m)	82.7%	84.1%

In both cases, the yield, is higher for the salted fish that have been salted with the RO-brine. However, the salt concentration of the water within the fish, showed the opposite, after brining, but not after salting as shown on Table 15. The lower Z_{NaCl} in the group treated with the RO-brine post brining could be due to both higher levels of other salt types, preventing the salt to be absorbed by the muscle, but also due to the lower NaCl concentration of the RO-brine.

Table 15: Z_{NaCl} value of the 2 groups after brining and salting

Group	Brining Traditional	Brining RO-brine	Salting traditional	Salting RO-brine
Z_{NaCl}	7%	3%	27%	28%

From those results it was decided to run a second trial with different salt concentration brines to evaluate if the lower Z_{NaCl} post brining was due to the salt content or to the type of brine.

Colour analysis

One of the main questions from shifting from the traditional brine to the RO-brine was that due to higher amounts of minerals and different salt types than sodium chloride, the colour of the salted cod would become more brown and yellow, decreasing the visual quality of the fish.

When the average yellowness and whiteness of each group was measured, no significant difference was found between them, both before, during and after processing as show on Figure 10.

Figure 10: Whiteness and Yellowness of the fish treated with the traditional and RO brines

pH

As more types of salt (potassium and magnesium chloride) were found in the RO brine, the pH value of the fillets was also checked throughout the process. Similarly, to the colour, no difference was found in the pH value of both the fish treated with the traditional and the RO-brine as shown on Figure 11.

Figure 11: pH value of the fish throughout the brining and salting process.

Second trial

Brines

For the second trial the initial brine was measured using a refractometer instead of the density meter. Salt content of the brines in the beginning is shown in Table 16 below along with the brine directly taken from the RO-container before adding any salt. Salt content was measured higher than what the refractometer showed.

Table 16: Salt content of the brines used in the second trial.

	Directly	7%		15%	
	Container	Traditional	RO-brine	Traditional	Ro-brine
Salt	5,2	9,0	8,5	18,7	16,9
Cu (mg/kg)	<0,03	<0,03	<0,03	<0,03	<0,03
Ca (g/kg)	0,6	0,08	0,39	0,17	0,67
Mg (g/kg)	1,84	0,05	1,11	0,09	1,67
Mn (mg/kg)	<0,01	0,03	0,02	0,06	0,05

Weight changes

The weight of the fish was measured at each step of the process and is shown in Table 17 along with the curing yield. Lower concentration of brine increases the weight gain of the fillets more than higher concentration brine, which was also seen in the 1st trial. However, after the dry salting step, the difference between the two concentration is lost. Traditional brined fish seems to lose less weight than the RO-brined fish, especially at 7% brine concentration, however the difference was not significant ($p>0.05$).

Table 17: Weight change of the fish in the 2nd trial after each processing step.

	7%		15%	
	Traditional Brine	RO-Brine	Traditional Brine	RO-Brine
Initial (g)	3478 ± 341	3626 ± 380	3782 ± 521	3466 ± 394
Brining (g)	3814 ± 364	3944 ± 400	3880 ± 536	3556 ± 412
Brining (%)	9,7 ± 1,1	8,8 ± 2,2	2,6 ± 0,8	2,6 ± 0,7
Salting (g)	2780 ± 308	2672 ± 322	2904 ± 412	2542 ± 355
Salting (%)	-20,1 ± 2,6	-26,4 ± 2,3	-23,3 ± 1,8	-26,8 ± 2,3

Chemical analysis of the fish

The individual fish was analysed for water and salt content after the two curing steps (brining and dry salting) as well as protein content after the dry salting. The results are shown in Table 18. No significant difference was seen between the traditional and RO-brine after the brining step. After the dry salting

step and trend is seen that traditional brined fish had higher salt content than RO-brined group, with significant difference at 15% brine concentration ($p < 0.05$) but not at 7% brine concentration ($p = 0.06$)

Table 18: Chemical composition of the fish after brining and after dry salting.

	7%		15%	
	Traditional	RO-brine	Traditional	RO-brine
Post brining				
Water	80,2 ± 0,4	79,5 ± 0,5	77,5 ± 0,7	78,8 ± 0,5
Salt	2,3 ± 0,3	2,0 ± 0,4	3,3 ± 0,5	2,5 ± 0,5
Post dry salting				
Water	57,5 ± 0,5	56,2 ± 0,6	56,6 ± 0,6	56,5 ± 0,5
Salt	22,2 ± 0,8	20,7 ± 0,4	22,4 ± 0,9	20,8 ± 0,7
Protein	20,2 ± 1,2	22,1 ± 0,9	20,3 ± 0,2	22,8 ± 1,3

Mass balance and curing yield

The mass balance evaluation of the process was done the same way as for the first trial and are shown in Table 19.

Table 19: Curing yield second trial, value found by weighing and then by mass balance based on salt free dry matter.

Groups	7% Traditional	7% RO-brine	15% Traditional	15% RO-brine
Yield (by weight)	79.9%	73.7%	76.8%	73.3%
Yield (by salt free d.m.)	85.4%	75.3%	82.9%	76.5%

Curing yield was significantly higher when using traditional brine compared to RO-brine at both 7% brine concentration and 15% ($p < 0,05$). Traditional brine at 7% brine concentration gives significantly higher curing yield than at 15% brine concentration.

Table 20: Z^{NaCl} value of the 2 groups after brining and salting.

Z^{NaCl} value	Post brining	Post salting
7% traditional	2,7%	28%
7% RO-brine	2.4%	27%
15% traditional	4.0%	28%
15% RO-brine	3.1%	27%

The Z^{NaCl} value for the second trial shows that using a 7% brine instead of 15%, the salt concentration of the water in the fish during brining is slower, while using the RO-brine instead of the traditional brine has a slightly lower Z^{NaCl} after 24h of brining. However, it does not seem to have a long-term effect, as all groups has Z^{NaCl} values over 26% (saturated brine), when the fish are fully salted.

3.3 Conclusion regarding quality, yield and food safety when using RO brine

In Conclusion, using the RO-brine instead of the traditional brine does not seem to have an effect on the salted cod quality, as neither the salt content, the colour, the pH or the chemical composition of the salted fish changed significantly compared to when the traditional process was used. Colour measurement did not show a significant difference in the average yellowness and whiteness of each group measured, neither before, during nor after processing. Between the first and second trial run, the yields that gave higher results were different between the traditional and RO-brine salted fish, therefore, no conclusion on the improvement of the yield can be taken. One interesting point that would need further research is that when the 7% brine was used in the brining step instead of 15% brine, better yields were found initially for the RO-brine and during the second experiment for the traditional brine. This raises the question about using less concentrated brine for the brining step to save costs, but further attention needs to be brought to potential microbial contamination if the salt content is lower in the product.

4 Environmental impacts & Life Cycle Assessment

VSV is currently importing considerable amounts of salt for its saltfish processing and using significant volumes of freshwater that is sourced from the mainland. If the company would reduce its needs for imported salt and freshwater, by utilising the freshwater and side streams from the water treatment plant, the environmental impact of the saltfish production would probably be reduced. That is at least the hypothesis that the authors of this report wanted to test. To do so, the authors performed a rather rudimentary life-cycle assessment (LCA) by comparing the environmental impacts of 16% brine, derived from seawater or freshwater (using the RO-brine and imported salt). The research question is, what is the difference between 1 L of 16% brine derived from seawater (a) or freshwater (b) and the system boundaries can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 12: System boundaries of 16% brine derived from seawater (a) or freshwater (b)

4.1 Materials, methods and assumptions

Key assumptions for the calculation were that the lifetime of the filter is 7.5 years, based on Lawler et al. (2025) and that the size of the filter is 1.8 x 1.6 m. For calculations on the environmental impact of conventional salt, the numbers in Ecoinvent database were used which are based on global averages. The built-in processes in Ecoinvent were adjusted to electricity production in Iceland as well as Icelandic drinking water. The LCA software SimaPro was used for the calculations and method ReCipE 2016 midpoint (H).

4.2 Results and discussion

The results show (Table 21) that the environmental impact of brine produced from seawater has a 32% lower carbon footprint than brine produced from freshwater, based on the assumptions listed above. It can also be seen that land use and water consumption are significantly lower, along with all other environmental impacts, with the exception of stratospheric ozone depletion.

Table 21: Environmental impact of 1 Liter of brine made from freshwater and seawater.

		Freshwater	Seawater
Global warming	kg CO₂ eq	7,1,E-03	4,8,E-03
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	2,3,E-09	8,5,E-09
Ionizing radiation	kBq Co-60 eq	1,1,E-04	7,1,E-05
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NOx eq	5,3,E-05	3,5,E-05
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM2.5 eq	1,4,E-05	9,4,E-06
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NOx eq	5,4,E-05	3,6,E-05
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	3,6,E-05	2,4,E-05
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	9,6,E-07	6,4,E-07
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1,3,E-07	8,8,E-08
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1,7,E-01	1,1,E-01
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1,9,E-04	1,3,E-04
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4,0,E-04	2,6,E-04
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1,8,E-03	1,2,E-03
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4,7,E-03	3,1,E-03
Land use	m²a crop eq	3,7,E-04	2,5,E-04
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	2,3,E-05	1,5,E-05
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	2,1,E-03	1,4,E-03
Water consumption	m³	8,6,E-04	1,1,E-05

The above calculations are made with the assumption that the salt brine is the primary product and does therefore carry all of the environmental impact of the process. The fact is however that the water treatment plant's primary purpose is to produce freshwater, and that the salt-brine is a byproduct. The salt brine should therefore only be allocated part of the environmental load, or should potentially carry negative environmental load as it saves both salt and freshwater.

5 Communication, dissemination and project management

Effective communication and dissemination, as well as tight project management with close collaboration between VSV, Mátís and Hatenboer-Water, were key to the success of the project and for sharing project progress and results. This was done through regular meetings, data exchanges and collaboration during the trials. Close collaboration with Hatenboer-Water ensured a good understanding of the membrane system performance and supported the evaluation of potential improvements to brine concentration technologies.

A [project webpage](#)⁴ was set up on Mátís website to showcase the project aim and impact, and updates on project progress and results were disseminated through multiple channels; both in the form of a news on Mátís webpage⁵ and social media platforms (Facebook and LinkedIn). News on the project were also disseminated in newspapers and popular magazines, such as Fiskifréttir⁶. These helped raise awareness within the fisheries sector about the potential of valorising side-streams from freshwater production. These publications contributed to increased visibility of the project's innovative approach and supported dialogue about circular solutions in the seafood industry.

Project management followed protocols developed by Mátís from planning, coordination of the work packages, data management and quality assurance with the support of both VSV and Hatenboer-Water. Tasks were organised according to the project plan, and milestones were reached as scheduled. All experimental work, economic assessments and environmental evaluations were documented and reviewed internally at Mátís to ensure reliability and traceability of results. Steering group meetings were held every 2-3 months during the project's lifetime. Overall, the communication and management approach ensured efficient progress of the project, transparent information flow, and successful dissemination of outcomes to both scientific and industrial audiences.

6 Acknowledgements

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⁴ https://matis.is/matis_projects/nyting-hlidarstrauma-vatnshreinsistodvar-til-framleidslu-saltpaekils-fyrir-fiskvinnslu/

⁵ <https://matis.is/frettir/aukaafurdir-afsoltunar-nyttar-til-sjalfbaerari-vinnslu-i-sjavarutvegi/>

⁶ <https://fiskifrettir.vb.is/paekill-sem-aukaafurd-i-ferskvatnsframleidslu-vsv/>

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8 Appendix

8.1 Appendix 1 – Current water treatment plant at VSV

The first stage of the current water treatment system at VSV is an extensive three-step pre-filtration to ensure the functionality and performance of the RO equipment.

- Coarse filtration (traditional type with sand and hard carbon) with a large filtration surface to remove suspended particles, such as sand, mud and organic matter from the seawater. The large surface leads to low scale formation and a safe filtration rate. The filter includes pipes, valves, deaeration and pressure measurement to determine the pressure drop. Backwashing is automatically controlled by pneumatic valves and also controlled by a time control that can be controlled manually on the control panel of the RO unit.
- Cartridge filters, located after the coarse filtration, act as pre-filters to remove small, suspended particles. The cartridge filter protects the high-pressure pump casing and the RO membranes, thus ensuring proper system operation. The cartridge filters can be replaced quickly, ensuring short downtimes and continuous operation.
- Automatic dosing unit for agents that prevent scale formation and lime accumulation, thus preventing deposits on the RO membranes. Deposits cause scale formation on the surface of the RO membranes, which reduces the performance of the RO equipment. Limescale prevention agents that prevent scale formation will reduce the number of cleaning cycles and increase the life of the RO membranes.

The main step of the VSV system is the RO device, which is divided into several units:

1. **High pressure plunger pump:** A high-pressure axial piston pump provides the required seawater pressure and flow to the RO membranes.
2. **Energy recovery device:** To reduce the energy consumption of the RO system a pressure exchanger type energy recovery system is applied and can save energy costs up to 40%. Pressure vessels with RO membranes. For the desalination process of the seawater, spiral wound seawater membranes are used. To guarantee long-lasting and trouble-free desalination of seawater into fresh water the RO (reverse osmosis) systems are designed with a large membrane surface. The RO system operates with a reliable membrane flux to prevent fast capacity decline (see Figure 13)
1. **RO permeate quality control.** The treated water quality is continuously monitored by measuring the electrical conductivity which increases as the salt content increases in the RO-fresh water.
2. **Fresh flush.** An automatic fresh water (from RO-water tank) flush program is initiated after each stop to prevent the RO system from scaling and corrosion. The saline water in the RO system will be replaced by fresh water, thus avoiding corrosion and membrane fouling.
3. **Cleaning In Place (CIP) unit.** To maximize the performance of the RO system a CIP- unit is included in the RO skid.
4. **Post-treatment: Neutralising filter.** The RO permeate hardly contains any natural hardness and the water has a low pH.

5. **Post-treatment: UV system.** DEMITEC® UV-Water Disinfection System, for drinking water treatment.
6. **Post-treatment: chlorination dosing unit.** Automatically operated pre-assembled dosing unit for chlorination of the RO permeate. For this application, a calcium hypochlorite solution will be used.
7. **Unit control panel.** The RO system is operated by a reliable control panel with touch-screen Hatenoer-Water microcontroller,

Figure 13: Schematic diagram of spiral wound seawater membranes as used in the RO-container

8.2 Appendix 2. The proposed additional filtration system

Description of additional equipment from Hatendoer-Water; nanofiltration (NF) and ultra-high-pressure RO (UHP-RO), designed to increase the concentration of NaCl in the UHPRO brine and at the same time partially remove the substances calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg) and copper (Cu) from the brine.

OPERATIONAL DESCRIPTION

Summary of concept design: The system consists of two steps membrane filtration. Brine from the existing seawater RO is treated with nanofiltration (NF) to lower Magnesium (Mg) and Copper (Cu) concentration. Antiscalant is also added before NF step to avoid the scaling on the membrane surface. This antiscalant will not pass the membrane, hence there will be no antiscalant in the nanofiltration product water. The product from NF is further treated with ultra high pressure RO (UHP RO) which will increase the TDS of the final brine up to 87,007 mg/l with high concentration of Sodium (Na) and Chloride (Cl). The permeate of UHP RO can be used for other processes where the water quality is allowed.

Pilot RO brine concentrator system

Complete pilot system for concentrating seawater RO brine from 5,3-6% to 8.7% salinity, primarily containing NaCl while reducing Cu, Ca and Mg levels.

The pilot system consists of the following equipment:

- ✓ Two-steps pre-treatment
- ✓ High pressure plunger pump
- ✓ Pressure vessels with NF and UHP RO membranes
- ✓ Unit control panel

The pilot system consists of the following equipment:

1. Two-steps pre-treatment

The system is equipped with an extensive two-step pre-treatment system:

- ✓ Cartridge filters, installed at the inlet of the system, for removal of small, suspended particles that is conveyed into the existing RO brine piping. The cartridge filtration protects the high-pressure pump and membranes thus ensuring a proper functioning. The filters are supplied with quick change cartridges.
 - ✓ Automatic dosing unit for antiscalant to avoid scaling on the RO membranes. Scaling is precipitation of hardness components on the membrane surface, thereby reducing the membrane performance. Due to high concentration of ions in the RO brine, antiscalant product is required to prevent scaling of these salts. Dosing of antiscalant starts automatically when the pilot system is started.
- 2. High-pressure plunger pumps:** Two high-pressure plunger pumps, one before NF membranes and one before UHP RO membrane, provide the required pressure and flow to the NF and UHP RO membranes.

3. **Pressure vessels with NF and RO membranes:** To concentrate the RO brine, special spiral wound NF and UHP RO membranes are used. To guarantee long-lasting and trouble-free filtration of RO brine water into concentrated brine water, the pilot system is designed with a large membrane surface. The pilot system operates with a reliable NF and UHP RO membrane fluxes to prevent fast capacity decline.
4. **External fresh flush:** An external freshwater flush program is initiated after each stop to prevent the brine concentrator system from scaling and corrosion. The saline water in the RO system will be replaced by fresh water, thus avoiding corrosion and membrane fouling.
5. **Unit control panel:** The RO system is operated by a reliable control panel with touchscreen. Hatenoer-Water microcontroller which provides a range of control functions:
 - ✓ start/stop with various safeguards for safe and reliable operation,
 - ✓ remote start/stop from the client's control system,
 - ✓ Micro SD, USB and Ethernet connection.

8.3 The importance of filtration and the different types of filtration equipment

Membrane filtration is used in process circuits to remove unwanted substances and particles that are not visible from liquids, such as in the production of drinking water from seawater. This technology is also useful for separating different particles or substances in solutions and this technology has been gaining ground in specialized processing processes.

The technology can be divided into subcategories; microfiltration (MF), ultrafiltration (UF), nanofiltration (NF) and reverse osmosis (RO) and this classification is based on the pore size in the membrane filters. The pore size in the filters affects their function and also on the pressure and flow rate during filtration through the membranes, and the holes in turn affect the pressure and flow rate during filtration. Membrane filtration provides the possibility of isolating different particles by size and thereby achieving the classification of different substances in certain production processes.

Table 22 shows comparison between different membrane filters i.e. the diameter of the holes in the membrane and at the same time the diameter of the particles that pass through (Retained diameter) and the pressure needed to run the equipment (pressure required).⁷

Table 22: Comparison of different membrane filters

Membrane Process	Retained Diameters (µm)	Pressure Required (bar)
Microfiltration	10 ⁻¹ –10	1–3
Ultrafiltration	10 ⁻³ –1	2–5
Nanofiltration	10 ⁻³ –10 ⁻²	5–15
Reverse osmosis	10 ⁻⁴ –10 ⁻³	15–75

Figure 14: Molecular weight cut-off (MWCO)/pore size - range for different membrane filter types

⁷ <https://wcponline.com/2009/02/10/membrane-technology-break-water-treatment/>

Figure 15: Overview of the efficiency of membrane filtration technologies⁸

Ultra-High-Pressure Low-Salt Rejection Reverse Osmosis (UHP-LSRRO)

Mechanical Vapor Compression (MVC), multi-effect distillation (MED)

Desalination can be achieved by membrane-based processes, such as reverse osmosis (RO) and electrodialysis, or phasechange-based (designated here as “thermal”) processes, including multi-effect distillation (MED), multi-stage flash (MSF), and mechanical vapor compression (MVC).⁹

Further concentration over 225 g/L using LSRRO membrane technology is challenging and potentially unnecessary, as according to the authors, this concentration is already sufficient for subsequent crystallization step.

⁸ Applied Water Science (2024) 14:169 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13201-024-02226-y>

⁹ DOI:[10.1021/acs.est.8b02771](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b02771) & <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wri.2025.100303>

Figure 16: Introducing ultra-high-pressure low-salt-rejection reverse osmosis for energy-efficient concentration of industrial brines

Ultra-High-Pressure Low-Salt Rejection Reverse Osmosis (UHP-LSRRO)

Mechanical Vapor Compression (MVC), multi-effect distillation (MED)

Desalination can be achieved by membrane-based processes, such as reverse osmosis (RO) and electrodialysis, or phasechange-based (designated here as “thermal”) processes, including multi-effect distillation (MED), multi-stage flash (MSF), and mechanical vapor compression (MVC).¹⁰

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¹⁰ DOI:[10.1021/acs.est.8b02771](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b02771) & <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wri.2025.100303>